

TABLE I

S.No.	Tertiary-N-Mannich base	Aromatic amine	Exchanged product	M.P. °C	M. P. °C	M.P. °C		I.R. (μ) NH
						Mixed with authentic sample	C = O (Ring)	
1.	V	Aniline	IX ^a	171-172	174-175 (9)	169-170	5.70	2.92
2.	V	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	X	157-158	156-157 (9)	—	5.65	2.95
3.	V	Methyl-4-aminobenzoate	XI ^a	210-211	210-212 (10)	210-211	5.67	2.92
4.	VII	Aniline	XII ^d	168	—	168	5.65	2.90
5.	VII	4-Aminodiphenyl	XIII ^a	186-188	188-190 (11)	190-192	5.65	2.90
6.	VI	Aniline	XIV ^{a,f}	164-167	167-169 (12)	164-167	—	3.00
7.	VIII	Aniline	XV	146	145.5 (13)	—	5.60 5.80	2.92
8.	VIII	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	XVI	135-136	138-139 (13)	—	—	—
9.	VIII	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	XVII	166-167	169 (13)	—	—	—
10.	VIII	Ethyl-4-aminobenzoate	XVIII	173-174	176.5 (13)	—	—	—

^a, Its i.r. was identical with the i.r. of the authentic sample. ^b, 5.80 (C = O ester). ^c, 6.50 and 7.40 (NO₂).
^d, Anal.: Calc. for C₁₄H₁₁N₃O₄: C, 58.95; H, 3.88; N, 14.73. Found: C, 58.87; H, 4.19; N, 14.69.
^e, 6.45 and 7.40 (NO₂). ^f, NMR: δ 5.65 (singlet-CH₂- β); 6.7-7.50 (aromatic 9H and NH).

Smith Kline and French Laboratories, Philadelphia, Pa. U.S.A. for spectral and elemental data.

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Possible Anti-Parkinsonian Compounds.

Part-IX.

Synthesis of 1,3,4-Substituted Catechol Derivatives

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Manuscript received 17 January 1975; accepted 19 May 1975,

SOME now 1,3,4-substituted catechol derivatives have been synthesised with a view to testing their anti-parkinsonian activity.

It has been confirmed by the biochemical, histochemical and neuropharmacological studies that catecholamines play a very vital role in the central control of motor functions. The researches of Carlsson¹ and Hornykiewicz² have further confirmed these findings. These authors demonstrated the loss of dopamine β -(3 : 4-dihydroxy-phenylethylamine) in the corpus-striatum and substantia-nigra of the brain. The level of other biogenic amines viz., norepinephrine and serotonin was also found to be lowered but not to the extent that dopamine is lowered. In addition succinic and malonic acid-derivatives have also been found to possess considerable anti-parkinsonism effect³. Based on these observations the authors thought it desirable to extend the work on catechol moiety with the expectations that these compounds might render better therapeutic results.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

N-Hydroxyethyl-phthalimide/succinimide :

The method described by Vogel⁴ was followed.

I. 1-Methyl-benzamido/phthalimido/nicotinamido/o-acetylsalicylamido-catechol (I) :

A mixture of catechol (0.01 mole), formalin (0.012 mole) and benzamide/phthalimide/nicotinamide/o-acetyl-salicylamide and few drops of conc. HCl was dissolved in 30 ml. methanol by warming. Subsequently the reaction mixture was stirred for 1 hr at room temperature and then refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. After removing methanol by distillation, a crude product was obtained, which

was washed with water and then recrystallised from appropriate solvent. Compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

[I. 1-Ethylphthalimido/succinimido-catechol (II) :

A mixture of N-hydroxyethyl-phthalimide/succinimide (0.01 mole) and catechol (0.01 mole) with few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid in 30 ml. of methanol was stirred for 1 hr at room temperature and then refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. Methanol was distilled off and the crude product thus obtained, was washed repeatedly with water. It was dried and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus obtained are recorded in Table 1.

3 : 4-Ethylene-dicarboxyphenyl-1-methyl/ethyl-amides/imides (III) :

To a mixture of succinic-acid (0.002 mole) and 1-methyl - benzamido / phthalimido / nicotinamido/o-acetylsalicylamido-catechol (I) or 1-ethyl-phthali-

mido/succinimido-catechol (II) (0.002 mole) and phosphorus-oxychloride (0.005 mole) was added slowly with constant shaking and cooling the reaction mixture. After the addition was complete, the resultant reaction mixture was heated at 115°-120° for 3 hr under anhydrous conditions. The mixture was cooled and treated with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution to remove any unreacted acid into acid chloride. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 2.

Pharmacology :

Compound Nos. 4 and 5 of Table 1 and 2 of Table 2 were subjected for the following screening procedures.

(a) Determination of approximate LD₅₀ values :

This was determined following the method of Weil⁵. All the compounds were found without any

TABLE 1

Compd. No.	n	R	M.P. °C	Solvent	Molecular formula	Analysis % Nitrogen	
						Calcd.	Found
1.	1	benzamido	140	ethanol	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₃	5.76	5.55
2.	1	phthalimido	145	ethanol	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ NO ₃	5.20	5.08
3.	1	nicotinamido	141-2	water	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	11.47	11.51
4.	1	o-acetylsalicylamido	164-5	ethanol	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ NO ₅	4.65	4.11
5.	2	phthalimido	135	ethanol	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ NO ₄	4.94	4.69
6.	2	succinimido	92	water	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ NO ₄	5.95	5.91

Note : Percent yield ranged from 65-75.

TABLE 2

Compd. No.	n	R	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % Nitrogen	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	1	benzamido	162-2	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₅	4.30	4.21
2.	1	phthalimido	115	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ NO ₆	3.98	3.85
3.	1	nicotanamido	111-2	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₅	8.48	8.41
4.	1	o-acetylsalicylamido	122-3	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₇	3.65	3.68
5.	2	phthalimido	83-4	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ NO ₆	3.80	3.91
6.	2	succinimido	85-6	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ NO ₆	4.41	4.29

Note : All the compounds were recrystallised from ethanol. Percent yield ranged from 50-60.

NOTES

toxic manifestations because they were well tolerated upto the dose level of 1000 mg/kg, intraperitoneally in mice.

(b) Anti-tremor activity :

For anti-tremor activity, the albino mice of either sex weighing between 10–15 g were selected. For each compound five mice were chosen and gum-acacia suspension of the test compound was administered intraperitoneally. After 1 hr, tremorine hydrochloride (20 mg/kg, intraperitoneally) was injected. This dose of tremorinehydrochloride has been shown to produce tremors, salivation, akinesia and rigidity in mice. After ten minutes of tremorine injection, the mice were observed for the effects of tremorine. No significant anti-tremor activity was observed behaviourally. However, the compound nos. 4 and 5 showed mild central nervous depressant activity.

These compounds were also subjected for anti-convulsant activity but none of the compounds was found to protect the convulsion in mice induced by pentylenetetrazole (metrazole).

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. Ram Gopal, Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow for providing necessary laboratory facilities. Thanks are also due to Prof. B.N. Dhawan, Head, Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics and Dr. J. N. Sharma of the said department, C.D.R.I. for evaluating the compounds. The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for providing a senior research fellowship to one of them (V.K.P.).

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Application of Thermographic Analysis in the Studies of Reclaimed Rubber Compounds. Effect of Sulphur, Stearic acid and Zinc oxide

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Manuscript received 22 January 1975; revised 2 April 1975;
accepted 2 May 1975

THE part played by reclaim in place of natural rubber in a compound has been previously reported¹. The present communication deals with the effects of (a) increasing the proportion of sulphur

and (b) stearic acid and zinc oxide in an accelerated reclaim compound.

Effect of Sulphur :

Table 1 represents the recipes of the compounds whose DTA thermograms are shown in Figure 1. The regions noted, in general, are (1) the T_m of the curative (here sulphur), being increasingly prominent with increasing proportion of sulphur, and (2) the curing region, followed by (3) a region at higher temperature, attributable to degradation and appearing in different shapes.

The thermogram characteristics of the curing exotherm indicate that the peak height is maximum in case of the compound containing the lowest amount (3 parts per 100 parts of rubber hydrocarbon) of sulphur (curve I), which when increased to 10 parts (curve II), the peak height sharply falls. No more appreciable change is observed on further addition of sulphur. When the fractional peak-areas^{2,3} (defined as the area enclosed by the initial base line, the rising portion of the curve upto the maximum height and the perpendicular drawn, from the maximum height to the initial base line) are compared, this area is also found to be greatest for the compound using 3 parts sulphur (curve I) and then the area decreases sharply on being transferred to the one containing 10 parts sulphur (curve II). Further increment in the quantity of sulphur does not bring any further significant change. With increasing proportion of sulphur initiation temperature (T_i) increases by a small extent whereas the peak temperature (T_p) is lowered; T_i and T_p respectively exhibit the maximum for the highest and the lowest proportion of sulphur. T_p in curve I is also remarkably different from that in other cases, where such difference is small. The slope of the peak with respect to the base line increases first slowly, then sharply, and finally slowly again as the amount of sulphur is increased upto 30 parts; above this proportion the slope value falls sharply. Compared to the other three systems, the ones containing 20 and 30 parts of sulphur show considerably higher slope values. Increment in the proportion of sulphur makes the curing exotherm gradually more sharp and distinct and brings about simultaneous changes in the shape of the thermogram in high temperature region (above 300°).

Effects of stearic acid and zinc oxide :

These are studied in both high- and low-sulphur compounds whose recipes are presented in Table 2

TABLE 1—FORMULATION OF COMPOUNDS* ANALYSED BY DTA

	I	II	III	IV	V
Reclaim	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
BA**	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Sulphur	1.5	5.0	10.0	15.0	25.0

* Formulations are based on 50% hydrocarbon content of reclaim.

** Butylaldehyde aniline.